

Dual-Band Filters Based on Dual-Mode Ellipsoidal Cavities

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Abstract— A dual-band passband filter with ellipsoidal cavities is presented in this paper. The filter exploits the ellipsoidal cavity fundamental mode for obtaining one of the two bands and its degenerate for obtaining the other band. The basic building block of the filter is the ellipsoidal cavity with input-output irises rotated with respect to the cavity axes. This cavity produces two poles and one transmission zero (TZ). One pole is exploited in the lower band and the other in the upper band. The rotation angles of input-output irises are used for the fine positioning of the TZ, either in the lower stopband, in the middle stopband (between the two passbands) or in the upper stopbands. Filters with two N-order bands and N TZs are obtained in a modular design by cascading N cavities. Each of the N TZs can be independently positioned in each of the three stopbands. The filter presents an inline geometry and doesn't require the use of internal elements such as posts for controlling the frequency band separation. To validate the proposed approach, a 6-pole dual-band filter with TZ in the middle band has been designed, fabricated with a 3-D printer, and measured.

Keywords— 3-D printing, additive manufacturing (AM), bandpass filter, dual-band, dual-mode, ellipsoidal cavity, multi-band, stereolithography (SLA), transmission zero (TZ).

I. INTRODUCTION

The demands for multiples services using different bands pushes the requirements of RF/microwave components towards more stringent performances. In this context, dual- and multi-band filters have become even more popular as they allow handling different bands in a single device, thus leading to size and cost reduction. In space communication, multi-band filters can be used to transmit noncontinuous channels in one beam, thus allowing the use of a single-power amplifier. Dual- and multi-mode filters have been already studied in different technologies. In [1], dual-band filters in combine technology are studied. In [2] instead, dual-band filters are obtained by using dual-mode cylindrical cavities exploiting TE_{11m} modes and their degenerate modes for obtaining low loss responses. In order to reduce size and weight, TM cavity technology has been used in [3] for obtaining dual-band filters. In [4], a similar principle was applied to TM cavities loaded with high dielectric constant ceramic puck, thus leading to an extremely compact dual-band filters. More recently, with the advance of additive manufacturing (AM), dual-mode spherical cavities have been exploited for the design of dual-band filters [5].

In this paper, a dual-band dual-mode ellipsoidal cavity filter where input-output irises can be rotated with respect to the cavity axes, is presented. The proposed structure presents three main advantages with respect to the one in [5]:

- 1) No intracoupling screws are needed in order to excite the two resonant modes.

Fig. 1. 3-D view of a dual-band filter.

- 2) Thanks to the input-output irises rotation, the coupling in the two bands can be independently chosen, this leading to the possibility of setting different bandwidths for the two passbands.
- 3) The modular design approach allows for the positioning of the TZs in each of the three stopband (lower, middle and upper stopband) while maintaining an inline geometry.

Regarding the last advantage, indeed the possibility of obtaining transmission zeros (TZs) positioned at the same time in different stop-bands is obtained in [5] with a non-inline geometry, where the two cavities are positioned side by side. In the modular design approach presented in this work, each TZ is related to a single building block [6], consisting of an ellipsoidal cavity with input-output irises. The reciprocal rotation among cavity, input and output irises determines three different typologies of building blocks in terms of TZ position: TZ in the lower stopband, TZ in the middle stopband, and TZ in the upper stopband. The proper selection of the building block typologies to be cascaded determines how many TZs the filter has in the lower, middle and upper stopband. This means that in the presented approach, the cross-shaped central irises required in [5] are no longer necessary. In the paper, it is shown how the three different typologies of building blocks can be obtained.

II. DUAL-BAND FILTER

The structure of the filter is illustrated in Fig. 1. The filter is obtained by cascading building blocks consisting in a dual-mode ellipsoidal cavity with input-output irises rotated with respect to the cavity axes. When building blocks are cascaded through nonresonating nodes (NRNs), TZs in the filter response have the same position of that of the isolated building blocks [6]. It is then clear the importance of the TZ position in each single building block. For the first building block, it is taken into account that shown in Fig. 2. This building block is capable of a TZ in the lower stopband. The structure is very

Fig. 2. (a) S-parameters with the TZ in the lower stopband. (b) Building block.

Fig. 3. (a) S-parameters with the TZ in the middle stopband. (b) Building block.

similar to that presented in [7], where input-output irises are rotated, one clockwise, and the other counterclockwise. The

Fig. 4. Normalized coupling values (M_{S1} and M_{S2}) versus the rotation θ .

Fig. 5. Topology of a 4-pole dual-band filter based on a pair of ellipsoidal cavities connected through NRNs.

main difference with the structure presented in [7], is that the frequency separation between the two resonant modes must be much higher, as here one resonance contributes to the lower passband and the other to the upper passband. This is obtained by a high eccentricity of the cavity. The theory presented in [7] shows that a fine positioning of the TZ is possible. Such theory also suggests how to obtain the second building block, having the TZ in the upper stopband: by exchanging the resonant frequency of the two modes. In other words, by increasing the cavity radius along x and decreasing the cavity radius along y , or with a rotation angle above 45° . However, the two building blocks described have a big limitation when used in a dual-band configuration since they cannot guarantee the isolation between the two bands. This isolation can be guaranteed by inserting a TZ between the two passbands. For this reason, it is introduced the third and most important building block with the TZ in the middle stopband. With reference to the routing scheme in the inset of Fig. 3(a), in order to obtain the TZ between the two resonances, the coupling M_{2L} must be positive (as opposed to what happens for the other two building blocks where it is instead negative). The sign change is obtained by rotating both input-output apertures in the same direction. Additionally, the rotation angle of input-output from Fig. 3(b) controls the values of M_{S1} and M_{S2} , as can be observed in Fig. 4, this leading to the possibility of generating two bands with very different bandwidths.

According to Fig. 5, higher order filters can be obtained by cascading building blocks by NRNs. NRNs can be obtained

Fig. 6. S-parameters of a 4-pole dual-band filter for different values of R_y ($R_{y1} = 13.5$ mm. $R_{y2} = 14.39$ mm).

Fig. 7. S-parameters of a 4-pole dual-band filter with TZ in the middle and upper stopband.

by quarter-wave waveguide sections or by long irises, however this would increase the filter length. This means that the NRNs are considered as starting point, then regular irises are used. In Fig. 6, responses of filters obtained by cascading two building blocks with TZ in the middle band are shown. As can be seen, in all cases the two TZs (one for each building block) are in the middle band. In Fig. 7, the filter has instead been obtained by cascading a building block with the TZ in the upper stopband, and a building block with the TZ in the middle stopband.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To corroborate the proposed dual-band filter, a 6-pole dual-band filter with all TZs in the middle stopband has been designed and fabricated. The lower band has a central frequency of 9.7 GHz and fractional bandwidth (FBW) of 1%, whereas the upper band is centered at 10.06 GHz and has a FBW of 1.2%. The manufacturing of the filter was carried out using a stereolithography (SLA)-based 3-D printing technique.

(a) (b)

Fig. 8. Photos of the fabricated filter.

Fig. 9. Measured and simulated results of the 6-pole dual-band filter.

Since the resulting components are produced in plastic, the proposed filter was divided in two parts for allowing an easy metallization. The filter was electroplated with a bright copper solution. Photographs of disassembled and assembled fabricated filter are shown in Fig. 8. Measured and simulated results are depicted in Fig. 9. Results show that the minimum insertion loss at midband is: 0.44 dB for the first band, and 0.29 dB for the second band. The minimum return loss is: 11 dB for the first band, and 21 dB for the second band. The lower band has a frequency shift of 10 MHz. No tuning screws were employed.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A dual-band filter using ellipsoidal cavities has been presented. The rotation between input-output irises and the ellipsoidal cavity allows an easy control of the TZ position, and the separation between the two passband can be easily controlled with the parameters of the ellipsoid. The dual-band filter is designed in an inline geometry and no internal elements are needed, thus simplifying the design considerably. For validation purposes, a 6-pole dual-band filter has been fabricated using SLA 3-D printing techniques. Good agreements between simulated and measured results is obtained, which proves the feasibility of using ellipsoidal cavities to design dual-band filters in 3-D printing technology.

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